

A Transmitter/Receiver Link for High Data Rate Polymer Microwave Fiber Communication at Y-band

Frida Strömbeck^{#1}, Yu Yan[#], Herbert Zirath[#]

[#]Microwave Electronics Laboratory, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden

¹ stfrida@chalmers.se

Abstract—A Y-band (170-260 GHz) ultra high data rate transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx), are designed and fabricated in a commercial 130 nm silicon germanium (SiGe) BiCMOS process. The link has demonstrated data rates up to 30 Gbps over a one meter polymer microwave fiber (PMF), using a carrier of 237 GHz. This is the first PMF link above 200 GHz reaching a distance of one meter.

Keywords—H-band, High data rate, PMF, Polymer microwave fiber, SiGe, Y-band

I. INTRODUCTION

Following the fast development of new high frequency semiconductor processes, to meet the public demand of high data rate connectivity, opportunities arise to use these processes to their full potential. Pushing the limits of the technology, transmitters and receivers can be realized at the limit of the process (around f_t). These high frequency, wide bandwidth links, are essential to future intra-box/module-to-module/in-cabine vehicle communication.

For these high data rate, high-frequency links, polymer microwave fibers (PMFs) is a robust, and cost-efficient solution [1]. In [2], data transmissions exceeding 100 Gbps over a one meter PMF at D-band (110 - 170 GHz) has been demonstrated. For frequencies above 200 GHz, [4] has demonstrated 35 Gbps over 30 cm at 260 GHz, showing the potential of dielectric waveguides above 200 GHz. By moving up in frequency a larger bandwidth can be achieved, thus potentially increasing the channel capacity [5].

In this work, a Y-band (170-260 GHz) PMF link, using a commercial 130 nm SiGe BiCMOS process, is presented and evaluated. Over a distance of 100 cm, data rates up to 30 Gbps are demonstrated with a carrier of 237 GHz.

II. CIRCUIT DESIGN

A transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) were designed and fabricated using a 130 nm SiGe BiCMOS process (B11HFC) developed by Infineon technologies. The process includes high speed npn HBTs with f_t/f_{max} of 250 GHz/370 GHz [6]. A block diagram of the link can be seen in Fig. 1.

For both transmitter and receiver an LO multiplier (times 4), a sub-harmonic Gilbert cell based mixer, and a differential cascode amplifier are used. A photo of the integrated transmitter is shown in Fig. 2, and the receiver in Fig. 3. Both circuits measure $3.4 \text{ mm} \times 0.7 \text{ mm}$ including pads, resulting in 2.38 mm^2 each.

Fig. 1. Overview of the transmitter and receiver PMF link.

Fig. 2. A photo of the transmitter. The size is $3400 \times 700 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 3. A photo of the receiver. The size is $3400 \times 700 \mu\text{m}$.

A. Wideband Frequency Multiplier

The F-band (90 - 140 GHz) frequency quadrupler consists of two frequency doublers (Fig. 4). Each doubler uses a class-B biased emitter coupled pair (ECP), which is provided with a differential signal from a wideband Marchand balun. A common base connected transistor is used at the combined collectors of the ECP to provide amplification. A current mirror biasing scheme is used for Q1 and Q2, so only one bias is needed (2.8 V).

Following the F-band quadrupler is an F-band buffer amplifier. The amplifier consists of six stages common emitter, with high pass interstage matching. Schematic can be seen in Fig. 5.

B. Balanced Sub-Harmonic Mixer

Both up and down converters use sub-harmonically pumped Gilbert mixer configuration, where the LO frequency is half of the RF frequency. The simplified schematic of the up converter can be seen in Fig. 6, and Fig. 7 for the down

Fig. 4. Schematic of one of the doubler stages of the F-band quadrupler.

Fig. 7. A simplified schematic of the sub-harmonically pumped Y-band down converter.

in Fig. 8.

Fig. 5. The topology for the F-band buffer amplifier for the LO chain.

Fig. 8. A simplified schematic of the Y-band amplifier.

converter. The differential signal fed into the base of transistor Q9 and Q10, which acts as a transconductance stage, is the IF signal for the up converter and the RF signal for the down converter. The upper level transistors (Q1-8) are switched on and off by LO, so as to produce the desired mixing products. The quadrature phased LO is generated by a combination a 90 degree F-band hybrid and two F-band Marchand baluns. The down converter uses emitter-followers as a buffer at the IF output to improve the IF output matching.

Fig. 6. A simplified schematic of the sub-harmonically pumped Y-band up converter.

C. Differential Cascode Amplifier

For output stage of the Tx and input of the Rx, a differential six-stage cascode amplifier is used. The topology can be seen

Some benefits of the differential cascode topology are common mode supply noise suppression and a high output power. As the Tx and Rx are designed close to the process' f_t , six stages were needed to get a significant amplification around 240 GHz.

III. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Measurements were done both in frequency domain and in time domain for a link demonstration. Both were done on-wafer using Cascade probe stations and GGB picoprobes.

A. Frequency domain measurements

For the frequency domain measurements, a Keysight PNA-X (67 GHz N5247A) was used together with a VDI Y-band extender WR 4.3 at the output of the Tx and as the input for the Rx. The LO was provided by a Keysight signal generator (Agilent 67 GHz PSG E8257D) which was synchronized to the PNA-X. For a balanced IF input an external balun (Marki BAL-0050) was used.

The measured conversion gain for the Tx is shown in Fig. 9, and Fig. 10 for the receiver. In both cases, an LO of 30 GHz and 4 dBm was used, resulting in a RF carrier at 240 GHz. A 4 GHz continuous wave (CW) was used as IF input. The Tx RF bandwidth is between 210 - 248 GHz, while the Rx bandwidth is between 195 - 245 GHz.

Fig. 9. Measured conversion gain for the Tx using a 4 GHz IF signal.

The saturated output power of the Tx, measured at 236 GHz, is 3 dBm.

Fig. 10. Measured conversion gain for the Rx using a 4 GHz IF signal.

In Fig. 11 and 12, the IF bandwidth is evaluated, with the LO frequency set to 30 GHz and 4 dBm. The 6-dB IF bandwidth for the Tx is 30 GHz, while the Rx has a more limited bandwidth.

Fig. 11. IF sweep for the Tx, with an LO frequency of 30 GHz and 4 dBm LO input power.

B. Time domain measurements

To evaluate the circuits in a link two probe stations were used. The data input was provided by a Keysight M8195A arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), which generated a pseudorandom binary sequence (PRBS-10) using root raised cosine pulse shaping with a roll off of 0.8. Furthermore, direct

Fig. 12. IF sweep for the Rx, with an LO frequency of 30 GHz and 4 dBm LO input power.

conversion was used. The output from the transmitter was coupled to the D-band PMF through a WR 4.3 probe to the receiver probe, leading to additional reflections and losses due to the frequency mismatch. The waveguide-PMF-waveguide loss is ≈ 20 dB at the carrier frequency.

The output from the receiver was captured using a Keysight Infiniium UXR Real-Time Oscilloscope (UXR1104A). Off-chip DC blocks were used at the data ports. A photo of the setup can be seen in Fig. 13, which shows the two probe stations and the PMF connecting the Tx to the Rx.

Fig. 13. The setup that was used during the link measurements.

The carrier frequency for the link test was set to 237 GHz, resulting in an LO input slightly below 30 GHz. In Fig. 14, captured eye diagrams of 20 and 25 Gbd can be seen, with measured error vector magnitude (EVM) of 11.3 %, and 13.6 %. The SNR was 19.0 dB and 17.3 dB.

Data rates up to 30 Gbps were tested, but the baseband was limited to 18 GHz bandwidth due to the setup, as well as the IF bandwidth of the Rx. Pulse amplitude modulation (PAM), using no pulse shaping, was tested at 10 Gbd, corresponding to 20 Gbps. Both eye diagrams are displayed in Fig. 15.

Fig. 14. Eye diagram of the received signal, using a carrier at 237 GHz. To the left, the baud rate is 20 Gbd with an EVM=11.3 %, and SNR=19.0 dB. To the right, the baud rate is 25 Gbd. EVM=13.6 %, and SNR=17.3 dB.

Fig. 15. Eye diagram of the received signal, using a carrier at 237 GHz. To the left, the baud rate is 30 Gbd with an EVM=16.7 %, and SNR=15.5 dB. To the right, PAM-4 modulation is tested, and the baud rate is 10 Gbd (20 Gbps) with an EVM=9.7 %, and SNR=17.7 dB.

Table 1. Comparison with other PMF links above D-band.

Reference	[3]	[4]	[this work]
Technology	65 nm CMOS	130 nm BiCMOS	130 nm BiCMOS
Modulation	ASK	ASK	ASK
Frequency (GHz)	180	260	237
Data Rate (Gbps)	10.3	35	30
Fiber Length (cm)	1.8	30	100

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, the potential of high data rate PMF links above 200 GHz, using a commercial 130 nm SiGe BiCMOS process is explored. Data rates up to 30 GHz were demonstrated, even though the setup was limiting and the PMF available was designed for the lower frequencies (D-band), resulting in extra losses. In Table. 1, the link is compared to similar work. This results show the potential of PMF communication in the 200+ GHz range and exceed the state-of-the-art in distance with data rates > 30 Gbps, by a factor of 3.

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